

The taboo gap: implications for adolescent risk for HIV infection

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Sub-Saharan Africa has the highest prevalence of HIV infection globally, where new cases arise disproportionately in adolescents, especially girls, whose incidence of new infections is 2-3-fold that of boys.¹ Gender norms and power imbalances play key roles in risk for HIV, for example affecting adolescents' condom use.² We quantified the role of norms in HIV acquisition using an approach developed for *The Lancet* Series on Gender Equality, Norms and Health,³ and to explain the findings through additional observational and epidemiologic data.

Analyses utilising a unique module of the 2007-2008 Zambian Demographic and Health Survey data – which asked attitudinal questions to men and women regarding other men and women – revealed that than 80% of surveyed adults did not approve of sex among unmarried young people.³ Yet, other data on age at first intercourse and at first union revealed that about 50% of adult women and over 80% of adult men had engaged in premarital sex themselves.³ Increased differences – or *discordance* – between professed attitudes of adults regarding premarital sex among adolescents and measures of adult premarital sexual activity were strongly associated with increased risk of HIV infection among adolescent girls. For every 10% increase in this discordance in a given community, the risk of HIV infection significantly increased by 27-28% for adolescent girls but not for boys.³

We hypothesised that the discordance was driven by, as we called it, a “taboo gap”: if premarital sex is unspeakable, individuals might hide their behaviour and refrain from seeking help.

Additional analyses led us to posit that the taboo gap was generated through reproduction of norms against premarital sex in homes, churches, schools, cultural events and even through development programmes, resulting in sex prior to marriage becoming a forbidden practice and

topic of discussion. The sustaining of similar norms can make premarital sex unspeakable and heighten risk for unsafe sex, especially for girls having sex with older men. Other social factors, such as food insecurity and poverty, may increase girls' HIV risk further by increasing child marriage and transactional sex. Biological factors such as differences in reproductive tract mucosa disproportionately increase girls' HIV risk at parity of exposure with boys.⁴ Adolescents seeking sexual and reproductive health care are often dismissed or shamed at health facilities, and face concerns about privacy, discouraging further care-seeking.

The taboo gap has broader implications for the health and safety of adolescent girls globally, particularly given that sex, especially premarital sex, remains stigmatised around the world. For instance, a study in Iran found that families played a large role in the generation of taboos around sex.⁵ When girls approached their parents with concerns about irregular menstruation, infections, or gynecologic pain, they were told that there was no need to see a doctor unless they were married. Consequently, these girls would tend to hide their symptoms for as long as they could, endangering their health in the process. By closing the discussion on sex and sexual health, parents played an important role in preventing their daughters from seeking necessary care. A study of adolescent girls in Zimbabwe showed how a lack of discussion about rape and sexual violence leads many girls to avoid reporting the abuse they have faced, as they want to avoid being shunned by their community.⁶ Several of these girls also mentioned that no one had discussed with them what menstruation was, which led them to think that menstruation was a sign of HIV. A study in the Sri Lankan Free Trade Zone found that taboos around premarital sex led boys to believe that rape was a method for triggering sexual desire in girls, leading to high rates of sexual assault that girls feared but felt they could do nothing about.⁷ Finally, a study in

Ghana found that the stigma associated with premarital sex and adolescent pregnancies led young mothers to be cut off from their communities.⁸

When a taboo gap around premarital sex is at play, service provision needs to ensure health care providers' capacity to address the needs of unmarried teens who seek sexual and reproductive health care without judgement. Analysis of gender transformative interventions shows that changing gender norms requires multisectoral action, multi-stakeholder involvement, diversified programming, and social participation and involvement of beneficiaries.⁹ Changing norms requires the inclusion of family members and representatives from schools, churches, and development partners in transformative conversations and actions while addressing gaps that exist within the health system. If community attitudes towards sex and gender change but the health system does not, adolescents will still lack access to the reproductive health information and services needed to practice sex safely. It will also be important to combine several approaches in addressing these norms, with interventions targeting both males and females. Peer health education approaches show particular promise.¹⁰

To combat the high rates of HIV infection in adolescent girls in Zambia, more data will also be needed about the current rates of child marriage and "Sugar Daddy" relationships. The recent rise in transactional relationships poses an important risk to adolescent health, and it will be crucial to address the underlying socioeconomic factors that may lead girls to engage in these types of relationships.

Finally, we suggest that a structured understanding of the taboo gap as a system of secrecy can help explain persistence of specific harmful practices. Researchers studying unspeakable practices might use the methods we developed to estimate the effect that secrecy can have on health.³ Their findings will be able to inform purposeful decision-making for effective policy and practice. Working to address similar unspoken practices in a context-relevant way may require cautiously facilitating cultural shifts to unveil the secrecy of those practices, changing norms within the health services as well as in the family, community, institutions, and structures (e.g., policies) to assure that those whose health is at stake can freely and safely seek help and support.

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